

Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City

Man Minh CAO

International University - Vietnam National University Hcmc; Quarter 6, Linh Trung Ward, Hcmc, Vietnam

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
12 August 2025

Corresponding Author:
Man Minh CAO

ABSTRACT

This research investigates the influence of Pet Attachment Level (PAL) on the diverse preferences of pet owners in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. By combining qualitative and quantitative methodologies, the study analyzes how PAL impacts preferences for product attributes, including Quality, Price, Design, Reputation, and Sales Environment, and how these aspects relate to Customer Satisfaction (CS) and Purchase Intention (PI). The data acquired from 292 pet owners was analyzed using Partial Least Squares-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), finding significant connections between PAL, CS, and PI. The findings highlight the importance of high-quality products, competitive pricing, and appealing retail locations in meeting the emotional and practical needs of pet owners.

KEYWORDS: Pet Products, Pet Anthropomorphism, Pet Attachment Level, Customer Satisfaction, Purchase Intention.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the number of dogs and cats adopted as pets in Vietnamese households has surged, reflecting a significant shift toward viewing these animals as cherished companions rather than mere functional animals. A report conducted by Euromonitor - a globally recognized leader in market research - recorded the total number of pets in Vietnam is at 28 millions (with 11.8 millions for only Cat and Dogs), this figure is predicted to have a stable growth of 6.8% annually.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concepts and Definitions

2.1.1 Pet attachment level

Pet attachment is a type of interaction and emotional bond between family members and their pets, according to Johnson et al. (1992). Zilcha-Mano et al. (2011) showed how owners may also use dogs as attachment figures. They also found that the anxiety and avoidance characteristics of attachment human-pet connections can benefit from the same orientation as human-to-human relationships. Apaolaza et al. (2021) added to the theories: pet attachment is similar to human secure attachment, with minimal avoidance and anxious attachment orientation. Pets offer unconditional affection and security, and are associated with lower levels of anxiety and avoidance than human relationships. (Beck and Madresh (2008); Green et al. (2018)).

2.1.2 Purchase intention

Usman and Okafor (2019) highlight, this intention is rooted in the consumer's readiness to buy a product or service. Andrade and Ferreira (2022) provide a broader perspective, defining purchase intention as the interplay between desire and willingness to acquire a product or service. Abdullah et al. (2024) suggest that both personal attitudes and social influences play a crucial role in determining an individual's likelihood to purchase a product or brand within a specific timeframe.

2.1.3. Customer Satisfaction

The consumer's conceptual response to buying and using a product, which results from weighing the costs and benefits of the purchase against expectations (Churchill & Surprenant, 1982). Tse & Wilton, 1988 stated that customer reaction to the assessment of the apparent discrepancy between expectations and the outcome following consumption. Emotional response related to a particular transaction that arises from comparing the product's outcome to a predetermined standard before making a purchase (Halstead et al., 1994).

2.1.4. Extrinsic and Intrinsic product attributes

Brečić et al. (2017) define intrinsic attributes as: quality can be objectively measured using intrinsic attributes. Brechan, 2005 added on the implication of intrinsic attributes as: "an important aspect of providing a solution for a customer's individual problem". Brečić et al. (2017) define extrinsic attributes as aspects that relate to the product but are not physically a part of it and have deep connection with the

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

actual product and need to be taken into account when assessing a product. Some common extrinsic factors that are essential are “brand, quality stamp, origin, store, packaging, production details, etc” -Bernués et al. (2003).

2.1.5. Pet anthropomorphism

The act of anthropomorphizing a nonhuman object exists daily, for instance: talking to pets with baby’s voices, attributing human’s emotions on pets and even dressing pets with fashion clothing (Apaolaza et al., 2021). Epley et al.,(

2007) stated that anthropomorphism is the human predisposition to imbue nonhuman entities, such as animals, with human traits, feelings, thoughts, motives, or intentions.

2.2. Hypothesis and Framework Development

2.2.1. Research framework development

Park et al. (2019) show to what extent the products attributes can affect customer’s satisfaction and therefore constitute their purchase intention:

Figure 1: Research Framework proposed by Park et al. (2019)

Apaolaza et al. (2021) developed a research model in which show variables that can affect purchasing behavior

of pet owners in the pet fashion sectors, by using human’s psychology via pet anthropomorphism.

Figure 2: Research Framework proposed by Apaolaza et al. (2021)

To fully comprehend the insights of Vietnamese pet owners when choosing the product for their animal companion when under the effects of pet attachment, a fusion

version of the two previous frameworks might cover the scope of the market’s facts:

Figure 3: Research Framework

2.2.2: Hypotheses development

- H1: Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer’s preferences of pet product quality.
- H2: Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer’s preferences of pet product prices.
- H3: Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer’s preferences of pet product quality
- H4: Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer’s preferences of pet product Design.
- H5: Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer’s preferences of pet product reputation.
- H6: Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer’s preferences of pet product sales environment.
- H7: Pet attachment level has positive and significant impact on Pet anthropomorphism
- H8: Consumer’s preferences of pet product quality have a significant impact on customer satisfaction.
- H9: Consumer’s preferences of pet product price have a significant impact on customer satisfaction.
- H10: Consumer’s preferences of pet product design have a significant impact on customer satisfaction.
- H11: Consumer’s preferences of pet product reputation have a significant impact on customer satisfaction.
- H12: Consumer’s preferences of the pet product sales environment have a significant impact on customer satisfaction.
- H13: Customer satisfaction of the pet products will directly affect owner’s purchase intention
- H14: Pet anthropomorphism might have significant impact on purchase intention

3. METHODOLOGY

This research will majorly use primary data (via survey) to analyze the correlation between the level of pet attachment to various purchasing intention’s determinants (pet product attributes and pet anthropomorphism). The quantitative approach supports the study objectives.

3.1. Data Collection Method

3.1.1. Target Sample

Park et al. (2019) collected a total of 180 responses with the candidates categorized by these traits: living in the city and owning pets. This research has the target sample being: respondents from Ho Chi Minh city and owning pets.

3.1.2. Sample Size

There are 29 items that related to the pet attachment level with their preferences on choosing pet products. Hair et al. (2014) stated that the appropriate number was at least 10 times the items/constructs in the research framework. Therefore, the optimal amount of survey needed for proper data analysis was around 290.

3.1.3. Data collection approaches

This research will utilize surveying as its main tool to collect data. In order to stay in track with the criterias for the respondents, this survey will only be spread among pet lovers, pet-related communities and groups on social medias. The survey is created by google form.

3.2. Questionnaire Design

There are a total of main sections in the questionnaires including: ‘Demographic’ section, ‘Pet attachment level’, ‘Pet anthropomorphism’, ‘Pet products attributes preferences’ and finally ‘Customer satisfaction and Purchase intention’. The questions within the survey are carefully established from observing from the previous

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

studies and adapting those questions into Vietnamese culture, more specifically within Ho Chi Minh city context.

3.2.1. Measurement Scale

The survey will be designed with a 5-point Likert scale from: 1 - Strongly disagree to 5- strongly agree.

Table 1: Measurement scale of Variables

CONSTRUCT		CODE	ITEMS	PREVIOUS STUDIES
Pet attachment Level		PAL1	Pet is a best friend to me	Apaolaza et al. (2021)
		PAL2	My Pet should be treated as family	
		PAL3	I often talk to pets	
		PAL4	I rely on Pets for emotional support	
Pet Products Attributes (Extrinsic and Intrinsic)	Quality	PAQ1	I am interested in Pet product’s ingredients and materials	Wang et al. (2015)
		PAQ2	I care about Pet Product Efficiency and Durability	
		PAQ3	I care about my Pet’s health and wellbeing	
	Price	PAP1	Reasonably priced	
		PAP2	Product’s value worth my money	
		PAP3	I accept to pay for pet product with equivalent price as human purchase rate	
		PAP4	I will prefer lower price product	
	Design	PAD1	Pet products are aesthetically appealing	
		PAD2	Environmental impact of the package	
		PAD3	Clear product information on label and package	
	Reputation	PAR1	The Product is trendy and highly recommended on the internet	
		PAR2	Everyone around me purchase this product for their pets	
		PAR3	High-end brands.	
	Sales environment	PASE1	Level of convenience of the store	
		PASE2	Level of accessibility of the store	
PASE3		Level of customer services of the store		
Pet anthropomorphism		PA1	Pets know how to express emotions	Butterfield et al. (2012)
		PA2	Pets can understand human	
		PA3	I treated pets with human values	

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

Customer Satisfaction	CS1	I feel happy with Pet product’s quality	Kim (2015)
	CS2	I feel satisfied with the design, price, brand reputation and sales environment	Apaolaza et al. (2021)
	CS3	I am content with my Pet’s human-like reaction to the pet products	
Purchase Intention	PI1	Pet product makes Pet look “more” human, making me wants to buy more	Apaolaza et al. (2021)
	PI2	Repurchase intention for the satisfaction fulfillment after assessing Pet Product’s attributes (Extrinsic and intrinsic)	
	PI3	I will have my pet reuse the pet products	

3.2.2. Measurement scale for ‘Screening’ questions

CONSTRUCTS	ITEMS	SCALE
Ho Chi Minh citizens	Are you a resident in Ho Chi Minh city ?	1 = Yes 2 = No
Pet owners	Are you currently owning and raising a pet?	1 = Yes 2 = No

3.2.3. Measurement Scale of ‘Demographic information’ questions

Table 2: Scales for Screening / Demographic questions

CONSTRUCTS	ITEMS	SCALE
Gender	What is your gender ?	1 = Male 2 = Female 3 = Other
Age	Which age group do you belong to ?	1 = <18 2 = 18-30 3 = 31-45 4 = >45
Employment status	What is your employment status	1 = Student 2 = Unemployed 3 = Self employed/ freelance 4 = Employed 5 = Retired 6 = Other
Pet Types	Which type of Pet do you currently own? (Multiple choices)	1 = Cats 2 = Dogs 3 = Fishes 4 = Rodents 5 = Birds 6 = Reptiles 7 = Other

Sources of purchase	Where do you usually buy pet products ? (Multiple choices)	1 = Pet stores / Pet shops 2 = Supermarkets 3 = Veterinarian 4 = E-commerce platforms 5 = Other
---------------------	---	---

3.3. Data Analysis techniques

3.3.1. Reliability Test

Cronbach's Alpha is one of the most common methods for assessing reliability. A value greater than 0.7 is generally deemed satisfactory, indicating that the indicators accurately measure the concept. Composite Reliability (CR) is another important statistic that provides a more nuanced assessment than Cronbach's Alpha. It takes into account the different loadings of each indicator to calculate a weighted average reliability score. Values above 0.7 for CR indicate strong reliability, implying that the construct's indicators consistently reflect the underlying variable.

3.3.2. Validity Test

Validity testing in Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) assures that the constructs and measures are correct and relevant. It includes both convergent and discriminant validity.

Convergent validity analyzes whether indicators of a construct are substantially associated, which is commonly quantified by the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), with values greater than 0.5 indicating good convergent validity.

Discriminant validity ensures that constructs are distinct from one another. It is typically assessed using the Fornell-Larcker Criterion, which states that the square root of the AVE for each construct should be greater than the correlations with other constructs.

4.1.3. Pet ownership status / type of pets

Figure 6: Types of Pets that respondents own (%)

3.3.3. Structural Path Significance Tests

Conducting hypothesis testing using SmartPLS3 for Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a reliable way for validating theoretical models by examining the correlations between latent variables.

Bootstrapping is an important component in SmartPLS3 hypothesis testing since it improves the reliability of the results.

The ability of SmartPLS3 to control multicollinearity through the computation of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is another significant benefit of utilizing it for hypothesis testing in SEM.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

4.1.1. Gender

The survey reveals a clear female dominance in the pet product market, with 59.25% of respondents identifying as female compared to 35.96% male. The data indicates that women are significantly more likely to be involved in pet product purchasing decisions than men.

4.1.2. Age

The study showed a large concentration of respondents aged 18 to 30, accounting for 70.89% of the total

The pie chart depicts the distribution of pet choices into four categories: dogs, cats, a combination of the two, and others. The largest section, 32.7%, includes those who own or prefer both dogs and cats. This illustrates the considerable proportion of pet owners who cherish both animals' companionship. Following this, dogs account for 21.0% of preferences, demonstrating their long-standing appeal due to their devotion, energetic lifestyle, and function in providing emotional support and security.

Cats are a close second to dogs in popularity, accounting for 19.8% of the chart. Their independence and adaptability for smaller living settings, such as apartments, are likely factors in this decision.

4.2. Reliability

4.2.1. Cronbach's Alpha Value

4.2.1.1. Pet Attachment Level

The overall Cronbach's Alpha of the Pet Attachment Level scale is.819. This score shows an acceptable level of internal consistency reliability.

4.2.1.2. Pet Anthropomorphism

The Pet Anthropomorphism scale has satisfactory internal consistency reliability, with an overall Cronbach's Alpha of.761. This result suggests that the Pet Anthropomorphism scale has great internal consistency dependability.

4.2.1.3. Product Attributes: Quality

Product Attributes: Quality scale has strong internal consistency reliability, as evidenced by an overall Cronbach's Alpha of.780. This demonstrates that the Product Attributes: Quality scale is internally consistent and trustworthy.

4.2.1.4. Product Attributes: Price

Product Attributes: price scale has good internal consistency reliability, with an overall Cronbach's Alpha of.738, which is above the widely acknowledged standard of.70. When we investigated the effect of eliminating specific items, we discovered an interesting finding. Specifically,

eliminating item PAP3 increased Cronbach's Alpha to.757. This rise implies that PAP3 may not be as closely linked with the other items on the scale or may induce measurement error.

- PAP3: This item will be eliminated from the construct

4.2.1.5 Product Attributes: Design

With an overall Cronbach's Alpha of.786 the Product Attributes: Design scale shows a fair degree of internal consistency reliability.

4.2.1.6. Product Attributes: Reputation

With an overall Cronbach's Alpha of.735, the Product Attributes: Reputation scale has good internal consistency reliability, above the generally recognized threshold of.70. We considered Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted to evaluate the effect of eliminating specific items. Notably, Cronbach's Alpha increased to.762 once item PAR3 was eliminated. This implies that PAR3 may be adding measurement error or may not be as closely linked with the other elements in the scale.

- PAR3: This item will be eliminated from the framework

4.2.1.7. Product Attributes: Sales Environment

"The Product Attributes: Sales Environment scale has a satisfactory level of internal consistency dependability, with a Cronbach's Alpha of.781. This demonstrates that Sales Environment scale has excellent internal consistency dependability.

4.2.1.8. Customer Satisfaction

The Customer Satisfaction scale has satisfactory internal consistency dependability, with an overall Cronbach's Alpha of.761. This demonstrates that Customer Satisfaction has great internal consistency dependability,

4.2.1.9. Purchase Intention

With an overall Cronbach's Alpha of.730, the Purchase Intention scale has a satisfactory degree of internal consistency reliability.

4.2.2. Composite Reliability

Table 15: Variable Composite Reliability

VARIABLES	COMPOSITE RELIABILITY
ANTHROPOMORPHISM	0.851
CUSTOMER SATISFACTION	0.864
DESIGN	0.876
PET ATTACHMENT LEVEL	0.881
PRICE	0.860
PURCHASE INTENTION	0.848

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

QUALITY	0.872
REPUTATION	0.894
SALES ENVIRONMENT	0.870

All of the variables in the table have CR values above 0.70, ranging from 0.848 to 0.894. This suggests that each construct's components are highly consistently assessing the same underlying concept.

4.3. Indicator Reliability - Outer Loadings:

Table 16: Indicator Reliability Result

ITEM	INDICATOR RELIABILITY	DECISION
CS1	0.857	
CS2	0.778	
CS3	0.837	
PA1	0.869	
PA2	0.899	
PA3	0.645	ELIMINATED
PAD1	0.813	
PAD2	0.843	
PAD3	0.857	
PAL1	0.807	
PAL2	0.861	
PAL3	0.798	
PAL4	0.753	
PAP1	0.811	
PAP2	0.839	
PAP4	0.810	
PAQ1	0.837	
PAQ2	0.837	
PAQ3	0.826	
PAR1	0.900	
PAR2	0.897	
PASE1	0.798	
PASE2	0.860	
PASE3	0.834	

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

PI1	0.795	
PI2	0.799	
PI3	0.823	

Most of the variables are able to pass the reliability test with indicator reliability with ranging from 0.753 - 0.899, which is a good thing since the figures for outer loadings test

is high and valid, however, PA3 (in Pet Anthropomorphism) only return a 0.645 for its indicator reliability, which made it disqualified from the construct.

4.4. Validity – AVE

Table 17: Average Variance Extracted result

VARIABLES	AVERAGE VARIANCE EXTRACTED (AVE)
ANTHROPOMORPHISM	0.795
CUSTOMER SATISFACTION	0.680
DESIGN	0.702
PET ATTACHMENT LEVEL	0.649
PRICE	0.672
PURCHASE INTENTION	0.650
QUALITY	0.694
REPUTATION	0.808
SALES ENVIRONMENT	0.691

All of the constructs in this investigation have AVE values between 0.649 to 0.808 which are higher than the suggested threshold of 0.50. This shows strong convergent

validity, meaning that each construct shares a significant amount of variance with its indicators.

4.5. Discriminant test - Fornell-Larcker Criterion Analysis

Table 18: Fornell-Larcker Criterion result

	PA	CS	PAD	PAL	PAP	PI	PAQ	PAR	PASE
PA	0.892								
CS	0.284	0.824							
PAD	0.207	0.325	0.838						
PAL	0.171	0.332	0.258	0.806					
PAP	0.156	0.343	0.179	0.260	0.820				
PI	0.203	0.493	0.212	0.264	0.320	0.806			
PAQ	0.189	0.466	0.323	0.312	0.334	0.427	0.833		
PAR	0.031	0.312	0.295	0.192	0.231	0.223	0.364	0.899	
PASE	0.214	0.399	0.341	0.221	0.296	0.284	0.417	0.253	0.831

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

The results show that the square root of each construct's AVE exceeds its correlation with any other construct. This study shows that each construct explains more

variance in its own indicators than it does in any other construct, providing strong support for discriminant validity.

4.6. Hypothesis testing

4.6.1. VIF - Collinearity assessment

Table 19: Variance Inflation Factor - VIF

	PA	CS	PAD	PAL	PAP	PI	PAQ	PAR	PASE
PA						1.075			
CS						1.075			
PAD		1.224							
PAL	1.000		1.000		1.000		1.000	1.000	1.000
PAP		1.178							
PI									
PAQ		1.415							
PAR		1.221							
PASE		1.327							

All variables have VIF values within acceptable limits, with the highest being 1.415. This prevents extreme multicollinearity and improves the regression model's

reliability and interpretability. The findings confirm that the predictors can be employed effectively while avoiding severe distortions owing to multicollinearity.

4.6.2. Coefficient of determination

Table 20: R-Squared - Coefficients of Determination

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
ANTHROPOMORPHISM	0.029	0.027
CUSTOMER SATISFACTION	0.318	0.309
DESIGN	0.067	0.064
PRICE	0.068	0.065
PURCHASE INTENTION	0.247	0.244
QUALITY	0.098	0.095
REPUTATION	0.037	0.034
SALES ENVIRONMENT	0.049	0.046

Based on the table's results, customer satisfaction has the greatest R Square value (0.318), meaning that the predictors account for about 31.8% of the variance in customer satisfaction. Similarly, purchase intention has a noteworthy R Square of 0.247, which indicates that the model accounts for 24.7% of its variation.

Other dependent variables have lower R square values, indicating weaker explanatory power of the model. Anthropomorphism, design, price, and quality have R square values ranging from 0.029 to 0.098, while reputation and sales environment have even lower values (0.037 and 0.049, respectively).

4.6.3. Effect Size

Table 21: Effect Size - f-Squared results (Matrix)

	PA	CS	PAD	PAL	PAP	PI	PAQ	PAR	PASE
PA						0.005			
CS						0.281			
PAD		0.018							
PAL	0.029		0.071		0.073		0.108	0.038	0.051
PAP		0.031							
PI									
PAQ		0.073							
PAR		0.012							
PASE		0.034							

Table 22: Effect Size - f-Squared results (Table)

RELATIONSHIP	f-SQUARED	LEVEL OF EFFECT
PA -> PI	0.005	NO EFFECT
CS -> PI	0.281	MEDIUM
PAD -> CS	0.018	NO EFFECT
PAL -> PA	0.029	SMALL
PAL -> PAD	0.071	SMALL
PAL -> PAP	0.073	SMALL
PAL -> PAQ	0.108	SMALL
PAL -> PAR	0.038	SMALL
PAL -> PASE	0.051	SMALL
PAP -> CS	0.031	SMALL
PAQ -> CS	0.073	SMALL
PAR -> CS	0.012	NO EFFECT
PASE -> CS	0.034	SMALL

Some notable impact sizes include pet attachment level on anthropomorphism (0.029), price on consumer satisfaction (0.031), and quality on purchase intention (0.108). These values are in the small to moderate effect size range, implying that these factors have a measurable but not dominant influence on their respective outcomes. Furthermore, the association between customer satisfaction and purchase intention is significant with an F-squared value

of 0.281, indicating a substantial effect size and emphasizing its importance in influencing purchase intentions.

Smaller F-squared values, such as those between reputation and customer satisfaction (0.012) or reputation and purchase intention (0.038), indicate that the effect size is negligible to small. Similarly, the impact of design on customer satisfaction (0.018) and the sales environment on purchase intention (0.051) is minimal. These findings

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

indicate that, while certain associations in the model are substantial and influential, others play a less important role in explaining the variance in the dependent variables.

Collectively, these effect size insights contribute to a better understanding of the relative relevance of each independent variable inside the SEM framework.

4.6.4. Size and significance of path coefficients

4.6.4.1. Path Coefficients and P-values (Direct Effects)

Table 23: Significance Testing and Path Coefficients: Total Direct Effects

	Path Coefficients	T Value	P Values	Significance (p < 0.05)
PA -> PI	0.068	1.108	0.268	No
CS -> PI	0.474	6.249	0.000	Yes
PAD -> CS	0.123	1.903	0.058	No
PAL -> PA	0.171	2.798	0.005	Yes
PAL -> PAD	0.258	3.513	0.000	Yes
PAL -> PAP	0.260	4.169	0.000	Yes
PAL -> PAQ	0.312	3.894	0.000	Yes
PAL -> PAR	0.192	2.791	0.005	Yes
PAL -> PASE	0.221	3.159	0.002	Yes
PAP -> CS	0.157	2.506	0.013	Yes
PAQ -> CS	0.265	2.671	0.008	Yes
PAR -> CS	0.099	1.671	0.095	No
PASE -> CS	0.176	2.565	0.011	Yes

The results show that numerous pathways are significant, as their p-values are less than the 0.05 level. For example, the path from CS to PI has the greatest impact, with a path coefficient of 0.474, a t-value of 6.249, and a highly significant p-value of 0.000. Similarly, the paths that lead from PAL to numerous constructs, such as PAD (0.258), PAP (0.260), PAQ (0.312), PAR (0.192), and PASE (0.221), all show statistically significant effects, with t-values greater than 2.7 and p-values well below 0.05. These findings

validate PAL's favorable influence on numerous parameters within the model, providing strong support for the associated assumptions.

The linked hypothesis is not supported by the path from PA to PI, which has a low path coefficient of 0.068, a t-value of 1.108, and a p-value of 0.268. Likewise, the p-value of 0.058 indicates that the path from PAD to CS is slightly unimportant, while the p-value of 0.095 indicates that the path from PAR to CS is obviously irrelevant.

4.6.4.2. Path Coefficients and P-Value (Indirect effects)

Table 24: Significance Testing and Path Coefficients: Total indirect Effects

	Path Coefficients	T Value	P Values	Significance (p < 0.05)
PAD -> PI	0.058	1.849	0.065	No
PAL -> CS	0.213	4.772	0.000	Yes
PAL -> PI	0.113	4.310	0.000	No
PAP -> PI	0.074	2.270	0.024	Yes

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

PAQ -> PI	0.125	2.159	0.031	Yes
PAR -> PI	0.047	1.761	0.079	No
PASE -> PI	0.083	2.465	0.014	Yes

The path from PAL to CS has the highest indirect effect, with a path coefficient of 0.213, a t-value of 4.772, and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a very significant association. Furthermore, the routes from PAP to PI (0.074), PAQ to PI (0.125), and PASE to PI (0.083) are statistically significant at p-values of 0.024, 0.031, and 0.014, respectively. These data lend support to the assumptions behind these indirect effects, highlighting the mediating function of the relevant variables.

Conversely, certain routes fall short of significance.

The path from PAD to PI, for instance, has a p-value of 0.065, a t-value of 1.849, and a path coefficient of 0.058, all of which are marginally above the 0.05 cutoff. Similarly, with p-values of 0.079 and 0.065, respectively, the routes from PAL to PI (0.113) and PAR to PI (0.047) are not significant. These findings suggest that although these connections might exist, there is insufficient evidence in the data to support the related theories.

Table 25: Significance testing and Path Coefficients: Specific Indirect Effects

	Path Coefficients	T Value	P Values	Significance (p < 0.05)
PAL -> PAD -> CS	0.032	1.565	0.118	No
PAL -> PAP -> CS	0.041	1.876	0.061	No
PAL -> PAQ -> CS	0.083	2.317	0.021	Yes
PAL -> PAR -> CS	0.019	1.207	0.228	No
PAL -> PASE -> CS	0.039	1.790	0.074	No
PAL -> PA -> PI	0.012	0.924	0.356	No
PAD -> CS -> PI	0.058	1.849	0.065	No
PAL -> PAD -> CS -> PI	0.015	1.614	0.107	No
PAP -> CS -> PI	0.074	2.270	0.024	Yes
PAL -> PAP -> CS -> PI	0.019	1.746	0.081	No
PAQ -> CS -> PI	0.125	2.159	0.031	Yes
PAL -> PAQ -> CS -> PI	0.039	1.953	0.051	No
PAR -> CS -> PI	0.047	1.761	0.079	No
PAL -> PAR -> CS -> PI	0.009	1.227	0.221	No
PASE -> CS -> PI	0.083	2.465	0.014	Yes
PAL -> PASE -> CS -> PI	0.018	1.801	0.072	No

The indirect effect from PAL to PAQ to CS stands out, with a path coefficient of 0.083, a t-value of 2.317, and a p-value of 0.021, validating the hypothesis of this mediating link. Similarly, the pathways from PAP to CS to PI (0.074) and PAQ to CS to PI (0.125) are statistically significant, with t-values greater than 2.1 and p-values of 0.024 and 0.031,

respectively. Furthermore, the path from PASE to CS to PI is statistically significant, with a path coefficient of 0.083, a t-value of 2.465, and a p-value of 0.014, highlighting the relevance of PASE's mediating role.

However, a number of paths fall short of the significance level. For example, there is no significant

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

indirect influence from PAL to PA to PI ($p = 0.356$), PAL to PASE to CS ($p = 0.074$), or PAL to PAP to CS ($p = 0.061$). Complex indirect pathways also fall short of significance, including PAL to PASE to CS to PI ($p = 0.072$) and PAL to PAD to CS to PI ($p = 0.107$).

From the analysis above, we can conclude that the Pet Attachment Level does in fact affect Purchase Intention Indirectly with the support from Product Attributes: Quality.

Confirming the very last Hypothesis: H14, therefore, we will adjust the hypothesis to match the result:

- PREVIOUS: PAL -> PI - Pet Attachment Level will have some significance to Purchase Intention.
- ADJUSTMENT: PAL -> PAQ -> PI: Pet attachment Level will have some impact with Product Attributes: Quality as mediating role.

4.7. Summary of Results

Table 26: Summary of results

Relationship	Hypothesis	Result
PAL -> PAQ	Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer's preferences of Pet Product Quality. (H1)	Accepted
PAL -> PAP	Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer's preferences of Pet Product Price. (H2)	Accepted
PAL -> PAD	Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer's preferences of Pet Product Design. (H3)	Accepted
PAL -> PAR	Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer's preferences of Pet Product Reputation. (H4)	Accepted
PAL -> PASE	Pet attachment level has a significant impact on customer's preferences of Pet Product Sales Environment. (H5)	Accepted
PAL -> PA	Pet attachment level has a positive and significant impact on Pet Anthropomorphism. (H6)	Accepted
PAQ -> CS	Consumer's preferences of Pet Product Quality have a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction. (H7)	Accepted
PAP -> CS	Consumer's preferences of Pet Product Price have a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction (H8)	Accepted
PAD -> CS	Consumer's preferences of Pet Product Design have a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction. (H9)	Rejected
PAR -> CS	Consumer's preferences of Pet Product Reputation have a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction. (H10)	Rejected
PASE -> CS	Consumer's preferences of the Pet Product Sales environment have a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction. (H11)	Accepted
CS -> PI	Customer satisfaction of the pet products will directly affect the owner's Purchase Intention. (H12)	Accepted
PA -> PI	Pet Anthropomorphism might have a significant impact on Purchase Intention. (H13)	Rejected
PAL -> PAQ -> PI	Pet Attachment Level will have some significance to Purchase Intention. (H14)	Accepted

Figure 7: Revised Research Model

5. IMPLICATION AND DISCUSSION

5.1. Pet Attachment Level on Pet Owner's Preferences in Choosing Pet Products

The results show that Pet Attachment Level (PAL) has a substantial influence on pet owners' choices for many features of pet products. Specifically, PAL was discovered to have a strong impact on Pet Product Quality (PAQ), Price (PAP), Design (PAD), Reputation (PAR), and Sales Environment (PASE). These relationships were all supported by hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H4, and H5, indicating that pet owners who are more attached to their pets have strong preferences for high-quality products, fair pricing, aesthetically pleasing designs, reputable brands, and a positive sales environment.

The fact that these theories are accepted emphasizes how crucial PAL is in influencing consumer preferences. The approval of H1, for example, demonstrates that pet owners who have deep links to their animals place a high value on quality, demonstrating their want to provide their friends the best. In a comparable way, H2's findings indicate that the price is an important consideration for these owners, who aim to get the best deal without sacrificing their dogs' welfare. These owners are interested with both the visual appeal and the brand credibility of the items they select, as seen by the favorable impact of PAL on product design (H3) and reputation (H4).

Pet owners prefer a fun and interesting buying experience, as seen by the considerable influence of PAL on the Pet Product Sales Environment (PASE) as demonstrated in H5. According to this study, stores should concentrate on developing spaces that support the emotional ties that pet

owners have with their animals in order to improve the entire shopping experience. Businesses may better customize their goods and services to satisfy the demands of extremely devoted pet owners by acknowledging the crucial role that PAL plays in consumer preferences. This will eventually increase customer happiness and loyalty.

5.2. Pet Attachment Level on Pet Anthropomorphism

The results show that Pet Attachment Level (PAL) has a significant and favorable influence on Pet Anthropomorphism (PA), as predicted by hypothesis H6. This finding suggests that pet owners who have a deep emotional attachment with their dogs are more prone to see human-like characteristics in them. This anthropomorphism can emerge in a variety of ways, such as seeing pets as family members or understanding their actions as having human-like feelings and motivations. The adoption of this idea emphasizes pet owners' strong psychological bonds with their pets, which impact their perceptions and interactions.

Understanding the link between PAL and PA has significant consequences for pet product marketers and developers. Products that appeal to pet anthropomorphism, such as those that focus on individuality, human-like qualities, or greater involvement, may appeal more to strongly bonded pet owners. This understanding enables organizations to customize their product offerings and marketing methods to their target audience's emotional and psychological demands, resulting in increased customer satisfaction and loyalty. The strong influence of PAL on PA emphasizes the necessity of identifying and capitalizing on the emotional relationship between pet owners and their pets when developing and promoting pet goods.

5.3. The Impact of Pet Product Quality, Price, and Sales Environment on Customer Satisfaction

Customer Satisfaction (CS) is strongly impacted by consumer preferences for Pet Product Quality (PAQ), Pet Product Price (PAP), and Pet Product Sales Environment (PASE), according to the results. The significance of these factors in influencing customer experiences and satisfaction levels is highlighted by the acceptance of hypothesis H7, H8, and H11. As seen by the substantial influence of PAQ on CS, achieving consumer expectations requires high-quality items. This research implies that pet owners place a high value on the quality of the items they buy for their animals, demonstrating their want to guarantee the pleasure and well-being of their friends.. On the other hand, PAR and PAD, which represent Design and Reputation attributes of the pet products, are eliminated due to lack of statistical evidence, which can indicate the insufficiency of those elements.

According to the results, pricing has a significant impact on consumer happiness, which is consistent with hypothesis H8. Pet owners look for bargains without sacrificing quality since they are price conscious. This suggests that competitive pricing tactics can improve customer satisfaction, thus it's critical for shops to provide a variety of goods at a range of price points in order to serve varied clientele. Customers' trust and loyalty may be increased by fair and open pricing, which raises consumer satisfaction.

As demonstrated by the acceptance of hypothesis H11, the Pet Product Sales Environment (PASE) has a considerable influence on customer satisfaction, underscoring the significance of the retail environment in influencing customer experiences. A welcoming, interesting, and practical retail space may significantly increase consumer satisfaction and promote return business. Retailers have to concentrate on establishing a welcoming environment, offering top-notch customer support, and making sure that pet owners' emotional and psychological requirements are met during the purchasing process. Businesses may greatly boost customer happiness and foster long-term success by putting quality, price, and the sales environment first.

5.4. The Impact of Customer Satisfaction on Purchase Intention:

The acceptance of hypothesis H12 suggests that Purchase Intention (PI) is directly and significantly impacted by Customer Satisfaction (CS) with pet items. This result emphasizes how important customer happiness is in influencing purchasing decisions. Customers are more likely to show a strong intention to repurchase and suggest pet items to others when they are pleased with the products' quality, cost, and entire purchasing experience. This clear correlation emphasizes how crucial it is for companies to continuously assess and improve customer happiness in order to cultivate loyalty and boost revenue. Retailers and manufacturers may successfully influence purchase intentions by putting the

needs of their customers first, which will eventually lead to long-term economic success and development.

5.5. The Indirect Influence of Pet Attachment Level on Purchase Intention through Product Quality

As demonstrated by the acceptance of hypothesis H1, the results suggest that Pet Attachment Level (PAL) has a considerable influence on consumer preferences for Pet Product Quality (PAQ). Furthermore, the direct effect of CS on Purchase Intention (PI) (H12) and the substantial influence of PAQ on Customer Satisfaction (CS) (H7) demonstrate an indirect mechanism by which PAL affects PI. In particular, pet owners who are more attached to their animals are more likely to choose higher-quality items, which increases their degree of happiness with them. This enhanced level of pleasure subsequently results in a greater desire to buy these things, which benefits PAL, PAQ, CS, and eventually PI in a positive feedback loop.

This indirect link is further shown by the acceptance of hypothesis H14, which shows that PAL has some relevance in affecting PI through the desire for product quality. This research emphasizes how purchasing intentions may be influenced by the emotional connection that pet owners have with their animals. Businesses may leverage pet owners' deep attachment to their animals to influence their purchase decisions by concentrating on improving product quality and guaranteeing great customer satisfaction. This realization provides insightful advice for product development and marketing tactics, indicating that emphasizing high-quality items may successfully use the emotional bonds that influence consumer behavior.

6. CONCLUSION

The study found substantial and statistically significant correlations between PAL and particular product features. Quality (PAQ), Price (PAP), and Sales Environment (PASE) were identified as key factors of Customer Satisfaction (CS). These findings revealed the essential significance these characteristics play in addressing the demands of pet owners who have a strong emotional relationship to their pets. Notably, hypotheses H7, H8, and H11 were verified, emphasizing the importance of these aspects in determining customer experiences. In contrast, qualities such as Design (PAD) and Reputation (PAR) had somewhat lesser effects on CS, suggesting that while these elements are still meaningful, they may not be as important in generating happiness among pet owners in this market.

The findings highlight the importance of important product attributes—Quality, Price, and Sales Environment—in determining customer happiness. High-quality goods that promote pet health and well-being, combined with competitive pricing tactics, are essential for creating pleasant customer experiences. Furthermore, a well-designed and engaging sales environment fosters emotional and psychological ties, increasing satisfaction levels. Pet owners,

especially those who have a deep emotional attachment with their dogs, cherish experiences that demonstrate care, trust, and excellence..

Customer Satisfaction (CS) revealed as a strong predictor of Purchase Intention (PI), highlighting its importance as a key intermediate in the consumer decision-making process. The results significantly supported Hypothesis H12, which proposed that CS had a direct influence on PI. This emphasizes the need of sustaining high levels of satisfaction in order to drive repeat purchases and build brand loyalty. Furthermore, the results showed that Quality (PAQ) acts as a mediator, with PAL indirectly influencing PI via its effect on CS.

REFERENCES

1. Andrade, L. J., & Ferreira, M. J. (2022). The influence of storytelling strategies on attitude and purchase intention. In *Advances in hospitality, tourism and the services industry (AHTSI) book series* (pp. 94–115). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-3436-9.ch006>
2. Apaolaza, V., Hartmann, P., Paredes, M. R., Trujillo, A., & D'Souza, C. (2021). What motivates consumers to buy fashion pet clothing? The role of attachment, pet anthropomorphism, and self-expansion. *Journal of Business Research*, 141, 367–379. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.11.037>
3. Beck, L., & Madresh, E. A. (2008). Romantic Partners and Four-Legged Friends: An Extension of Attachment Theory to Relationships with Pets. *Anthrozoös*, 21(1), 43–56. <https://doi.org/10.2752/089279308x274056>
4. Bernués, A., Olaizola, A., & Corcoran, K. (2003). Extrinsic attributes of red meat as indicators of quality in Europe: an application for market segmentation. *Food Quality and Preference*, 14(4), 265–276. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0950-3293\(02\)00085-x](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0950-3293(02)00085-x)
5. Brechan, I. (2005). The different effect of primary and secondary product attributes on customer satisfaction. *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 27(3), 441–458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2005.10.003>
6. Brečić, R., Mesić, Ž., & Cerjak, M. (2017). Importance of intrinsic and extrinsic quality food characteristics by different consumer segments. *British Food Journal*, 119(4), 845–862. <https://doi.org/10.1108/bfj-06-2016-0284>
7. Butterfield, M. E., Hill, S. E., & Lord, C. G. (2012). Mangy mutt or furry friend? Anthropomorphism promotes animal welfare. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology*, 48(4), 957–960. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jesp.2012.02.010>
8. Churchill, G. A., & Surprenant, C. (1982). An Investigation into the Determinants of Customer Satisfaction. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 19(4), 491. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3151722>
9. Epley, N., Waytz, A., & Cacioppo, J. T. (2007). On seeing human: A three-factor theory of anthropomorphism. *Psychological Review*, 114(4), 864–886. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.114.4.864>
10. Green, J. D., Coy, A. E., & Mathews, M. A. (2018). Attachment anxiety and avoidance influence pet choice and pet-directed behaviors. *Anthrozoös*, 31(4), 475–494. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08927936.2018.1482117>
11. Hair, J. F., Jr, Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & Kuppelwieser, V. G. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106–121. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb-10-2013-0128>
12. Halstead, D., Hartman, D., & Schmidt, S. L. (1994). Multisource effects on the satisfaction formation process. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 22(2), 114–129. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070394222002>
13. Johnson, T. P., Garrity, T. F., & Stallones, L. (1992). Psychometric Evaluation of the Lexington Attachment to Pets Scale (LAPS). *Anthrozoös*, 5(3), 160–175. <https://doi.org/10.2752/089279392787011395>
14. Kim, 구. D. W. K. . 이. S. M. L., . 김. I. H. (2015). 커피전문점 이용객의 브랜드 일체감이 관여도, 고객만족, 그리고 브랜드 충성도에 미치는 영향: 프랜차이즈 가맹점을 중심으로. 학술논문검색사이트 KISS. <https://kiss.kstudy.com/Detail/Ar?key=3319598>
15. Park, E., Shin, J., & Park, M. (2019). A Study on the Relationship among Attachment to Pet, Purchasing Attributes of Pet Products, Satisfaction, and Behavioral Intention. *Journal of the Korea Academia-Industrial Cooperation Society*, 20(9), 279–289. <https://doi.org/10.5762/kais.2019.20.9.279>
16. Tse, D. K., & Wilton, P. C. (1988). Models of Consumer Satisfaction Formation: an extension. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 25(2), 204. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3172652>
17. Usman, A., & Okafor, S. (2019). Exploring the relationship between social media and social influence. In *Advances in marketing, customer relationship management, and e-services book series* (pp. 83–103). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-7344-9.ch004>
18. Wang, J., Park, J., Choi, N., Ha, S., & Oh, D. (2015). Microbiological analysis of rice cake processing in

“Impact of Pet Attachment Levels on the Determinants of Purchase Intentions Among Pet Owners in Ho Chi Minh City”

Korea. *Journal of Food Protection*, 79(1), 157–162.
<https://doi.org/10.4315/0362-028x.jfp-15-237>

19. Zilcha-Mano, S., Mikulincer, M., & Shaver, P. R. (2011). An attachment perspective on human–pet relationships: Conceptualization and assessment of pet attachment orientations. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 45(4), 345–357.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2011.04.001>